

Language Identification and Corpus Creation for Telugu-English Code-Mixed Text

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ABSTRACT

Code-mixed text and speech are widely prevalent in multilingual societies, allowing users to switch seamlessly between multiple languages. AI models trained on monolingual corpora, such as English, perform poorly when user utterances contain a mix of languages, and must therefore be trained on code-mixed corpora. Telugu is one of the most prominent languages in India. However, there is a scarcity of labeled datasets and large corpora in Telugu-English code-mixed form, which are essential for developing supervised machine learning models. In this paper, we create an annotated dataset of 25,006 Telugu-English code-mixed YouTube comments labeled at the word level, comprising 332,403 tokens, and develop a word-level language identification system. Various machine learning and deep learning systems are experimented with, and the BiLSTM-CRF (Bidirectional Long Short-Term Memory-Conditional Random Field) model achieved an F1 score of 96%. The trained language identification model is then used to automatically collect the largest Telugu-English code-mixed corpus comprising 3.6 million comments.

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1. INTRODUCTION

Code-mixing refers to the use of more than one language in text or speech. Ref[1] defines code-mixing as a fluid alternation between two or more languages during a conversation or utterance. Telugu is a native language spoken in the southern Indian states of Andhra Pradesh and Telangana, with a combined population of more than 90 million. It belongs to the Dravidian family of languages and is agglutinative, suffix-heavy, and follows a Subject-Object-Verb (SOV) word order. Telugu morphology includes rich case markings, extensive postpositions, and complex verb inflections, making it structurally distinct from English. Telugu-English code mixed text appears frequently in social media posts. With much online content being generated in code-mixed form, there are commercial benefits for companies to process such text, such as the development of chatbots and voice assistants. Also, much content is being generated on social media, including hate speech, offensive language, trolls, fake information, targeting specific groups and communities, etc. Processing of such content is important for government agencies.

Language identification is a key step in code-mixed applications but remains challenging in context of social media due to its informal nature. Spelling errors (“distrub” for “disturb”), abbreviations (“u” for “you”), elongations (“broooo” for “bro”), and transliteration variations (e.g., the transliterated Telugu word “istam” may also be written as “ishtam” or “estam”) reduce system performance. Also, mixing may occur both across words and within single words, as in “collegeki” (English “college” + Telugu suffix “ki”). Given Telugu’s morphological richness and agglutinative nature, such fused forms are common, that make simple dictionary-based approaches insufficient for effective language identification.

India’s multilingual social landscape has led to research on code-mixed text, particularly in Hindi English, Bengali-English, Malayalam-English, and Kannada-English. Early work explored traditional approaches such as SVMs and CRFs with character n-grams, dictionary features, and capitalization cues ([2]

– [4]). Subsequent studies introduced neural models, including LSTM (Long Short-Term Memory) and BiLSTM-CRF, often leveraging character and phonetic level representations ([5]–[7]). More recent efforts increasingly adopt transformer based architectures, with models such as BERT (Bi-directional Encoder Representations with Transformers), DistilBERT, and XLM-RoBERTa achieving state-of-the-art performance on word-level language identification across multiple Indian language pairs ([8]–[11]). Collectively, these works demonstrate the evolution from feature-driven machine learning models to deep learning and pretrained transformers for code-mixed language identification in Indian languages.

A smaller but growing body of work has addressed Telugu-English code-mixed language identification. Early studies relied on CRF (Conditional Random Field) models with lexical, character, and contextual features but achieved modest F1 scores (45–52%) due to small datasets and annotation limitations ([12]–[13]). Subsequent efforts improved performance using richer features and hybrid models: a two-stage CRF approach achieved 75% on FIRE 2015 (Forum for Information Retrieval Conference) [14], while CRF with expanded feature sets reached 91% on ICON (International Conference on Natural Language Processing) 2015 data [15]. Deep learning approaches pushed performance further: LSTM, CNN (Convolutional Neural Network), and BiLSTM-based architectures trained on larger blog and Twitter datasets reported accuracies up to 99% [16]. More recently, transformer-based methods such as BERT with CNN extensions have been applied, achieving around 90% accuracy but lower macro-F1 due to sparse tag distributions [17]. Overall, progress in Telugu-English code-mixed language identification mirrors broader trends, moving from feature-driven CRFs to neural and transformer-based models.

Only a few Telugu-English code-mixed datasets with language annotation exist. The ICON 2015 POSMISMT (NLP Tools Contest on POS Tagging For Code-mixed Indian Social Media Text) dataset includes 1,987 sentences (29,503 words) with POS (Part of Speech) and language tags [15], while FIRE 2015 provided 605 utterances with 7,002 tags for Telugu [18]. Ref [16] created two datasets: one from blogs (9,657 sentences, 13,648 words) and another from Twitter (24,404 sentences, 212,020 words). Ref [19] developed a corpus for aggression detection with language annotation on 3,361 tweets. Overall, the availability of large Telugu-English corpora remains limited [20], with most datasets sourced from Twitter and Facebook. To address this gap, in this work we manually annotated language tags for 25,006 sentences comprising 3,32,403 individual tokens. This labeled data is used to train a language identification system. The trained model is then applied to social media posts to identify only comments that are code-mixed in nature. In this way, a large corpus of 3.6 million Telugu-English code-mixed comments is built. While the BiLSTM-CRF is a standard architecture, our contribution lies in how we adapt and extend it for Telugu-English code-mixed NLP. We integrate language-specific lexical and contextual features, train on a manually annotated 25k-sentence dataset of realistic social media comments, and use the model to automatically collect a large-scale 3.6 million sentence corpus.

While previous multilingual NLP studies have focused primarily on monolingual or clean bilingual datasets, recent research emphasizes the importance of code-mixed corpora in training more contextually aware multilingual models ([21]–[22]). Recent advances in multilingual LLMs (Large Language Models) such as mBERT, XLM-R, and GPT-style multilingual architectures have demonstrated strong cross-lingual transfer capabilities. However, these models often struggle with code-mixed and transliterated data, due to the lack of representative bilingual data. Our Telugu-English corpus directly addresses this gap by providing large scale, naturally occurring social media data that can enhance LLM adaptation and evaluation in code-mixed scenarios. Moreover, integrating sociolinguistic analysis – examining language choice, mixing frequency, and functional switching – offers a richer understanding of multilingual behavior in online communication. Our dataset aligns with this interdisciplinary direction, bridging computational and sociolinguistic perspectives. This work can be extended in future works to provide insights into how speakers negotiate linguistic boundaries in informal digital settings.

Building on the broader applicability of our datasets to multilingual LLMs and sociolinguistic studies, we also envision their use in fostering community-driven benchmarking efforts for code-mixed NLP. The proposed Telugu-English code-mixed corpus opens opportunities for designing shared tasks and benchmark evaluations to advance research in multilingual and social media NLP. Future work can include developing standardized benchmarks for code-mixed language identification (CM-LID), named entity recognition (CM-NER), part-of-speech tagging (CM-POS), sentiment analysis (CM-Sentiment), and dependency parsing (CM-DEP). Establishing these benchmarks will enable consistent evaluation across models and promote community participation through shared tasks similar to ICON and SemEval initiatives. Such efforts would not only facilitate systematic comparison of approaches on Telugu-English data but also contribute to building robust, generalizable models capable of handling informal and hybrid linguistic phenomena in multilingual digital communication.

2. METHOD

2.1. Data

The data used in this work consists of Telugu-English code-mixed comments extracted from YouTube videos. A total of 50.82 million comments were initially downloaded from 520 YouTube channels that post content in Telugu using the YouTube API. The videos cover various domains, including politics, films, sports, and entertainment. Of these, 25,006 comments were selected and annotated for language tags at the word level. This data is used as labeled data for developing the language identification system, which is then used to automatically expand the corpus. The flow chart of the corpus creation pipeline is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Flowchart of corpus creation pipeline

The 25,006 comments annotated manually are subjected to a series of pre-processing steps to ensure data quality and consistency. Each comment is required to be at least four words long, thereby eliminating very short comments. To maintain the focus on code-mixed text, only comments containing at least one Telugu word and one English word are considered, while those written entirely in either language are excluded. Since all comments are written in Roman script, this script uniformity is preserved. Repeated character sequences longer than two were trimmed (for example, “soooooo” is reduced to “soo”) to control exaggerated spellings. Punctuation symbols such as periods, commas, quotes, and hyphens are retained, as were usernames and hashtags, whereas smileys are discarded. Finally, case sensitivity is maintained throughout the dataset by preserving the original casing of words.

The data is split 70/10/20 to create training, validation and test sets, respectively. The validation set is used to tune the model’s hyperparameters. The final annotated dataset contains 25,006 comments comprising 332,403 tokens. The average number of tokens per comment is 13.29. The count of unique tokens is 66,591. The number of tokens under each category is provided in Table 1.

Each token in the dataset is annotated with one of four categories: Telugu, English, Named Entity, or Other. The Other category covers tokens that do not fall strictly under the first three labels, including numbers (e.g., 2024), abbreviations (e.g., plz), acronyms (e.g., YSRCP), hashtags (e.g., #iplt20), fusion words that blend English or named entities with Telugu suffixes (e.g., collegeki, trainlo), as well as occasional Hindi words. Annotation is performed by a single annotator proficient in both Telugu and English using Doccano [23]. It took around 400 hours to complete the annotation. The dataset is publicly released and available on GitHub [24].

Table 1. Number of tokens in the language identification dataset under each category

Label	Description	Example	Count	% of total tokens	Unique tokens	% of unique tokens
Telugu	Telugu words written in Roman script	“evaru”	191,420	57.59	45,477	68.29
English	English words	“district”	90,255	27.15	11,787	17.70
Named entity	Words indicating names of persons, locations, organizations, etc.	“kakinada”	25,861	7.78	6,310	9.48
Other (of which, fusion words)	Numbers, symbols, mixed words, etc. English stem + Telugu suffix	2024, “?” “fastga” ”arealo”	24,867 (1,048)	7.48 (0.32)	3,017 (93)	4.53 (0.14)
Total			332,403	100.00	66,591	

2.2. Methodology

In addition to establishing baselines using traditional machine learning models such as Logistic Regression, Support Vector Machine (SVM), and Random Forest, we have experimented with deep learning models such as the BiLSTM-CRF and BERT [25] transformer model. For BiLSTM-CRF model, we adopt the architecture from [26], designed for neural sequence labeling, consisting of three layers as shown in Figure 2. The first layer is a character sequence layer that encodes character-level information using a CNN. The character sequence information of the word encoded by CNN is concatenated with word vector and hand-crafted features such as suffixes, capitalization, etc. The resulting word representations are passed to the second layer, which is a word sequence layer, where a Bi-LSTM captures bidirectional context. Finally, the CRF inference layer assigns labels (Telugu or English or Named Entity or Others) to words while modeling label dependencies across the sequence.

The BiLSTM-CRF model incorporates a diverse set of hand-crafted features designed to capture lexical, phonetic, and contextual properties of words. These include basic lexical features such as word length, the number of special characters, the number of digits, and whether the word is a single character (e.g., ‘a’, ‘e’, ‘y’). Case-based features account for whether all letters in a word are in uppercase or whether only the first letter is capitalized. Dictionary-based features identify whether a word is present in the English dictionary (sourced from the english-words 2.0.1 project [27] containing 370,104 words) or in the Telugu dictionary (sourced from the Aksharantar [28] project, which provides 2,447,503 transliterated Telugu words), and whether a word appears exclusively in one dictionary but not both. Phonetic information is captured using Soundex [29] encoding, while sub-word patterns are extracted by considering the first two and three letters and the last two and three letters of each word (e.g., for *meelantivaru*, the prefixes are “me” and “mee,” and the suffixes are “ru” and “aru”). The relative importance of words in the corpus is captured using TF-IDF (Term Frequency–Inverse Document Frequency). Finally, contextual features are incorporated by including the previous two and next two words surrounding the current word.

The BiLSTM-CRF model is implemented using NCRF++ [26]. A CNN encodes character sequences, which are concatenated with 100 dimensional word embeddings and 20 dimensional hand-crafted feature embeddings. A BiLSTM (hidden size 200) extracts context, and a CRF layer predicts the best label sequence. The model is trained with Adagrad (batch size 10, learning rate 0.015, decay 0.05), 12 regularization ($1e-8$), dropout (0.5), and a maximum sequence length of 250, over 25 epochs.

BERT is a transformer encoder stack that is used to learn contextual information between words in a text. Since such models require large amounts of data to train and such a large amount of Telugu-English code-mixed data is not available, we have used transfer learning, wherein a pre-trained language model HingBERT-LID [11] is obtained from the [Huggingface](#) Transformers library. This is a base BERT model first trained on HingBERT [11], a corpus of Hindi-English code-mixed text comprising 47.79 million sentences, which is then fine-tuned for the task of Hindi-English code-mixed language identification. For our task of language identification of Telugu-English code-mixed text, we fine-tuned this HingBERT-LID model using our annotated dataset comprising 25,006 sentences. The parameters used for fine-tuning the HingBERT-LID model are Adam optimizer with a learning rate of $2e-5$, batch size of 8 and number of epochs at 5. The BERT configuration for the HingBERT-LID model uses 12 attention heads, 12 hidden layers, max position embedding of 512, dropout of 0.1, gelu activation for hidden units, hidden size of 768 and BertTokenizerFast tokenizer.

Figure 2. Architecture of the BiLSTM-CRF model based on model proposed by Yang et al in [26]. Character-level features are encoded using a CNN and concatenated with word embeddings and hand-crafted features. A BiLSTM captures bidirectional context, and a CRF layer performs sequence-level label inference

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1. Results

The evaluation of the proposed system is performed using Precision, Recall, and F1-metrics. For F1, we report the macro average and weighted average scores. The performance of traditional machine learning algorithms and deep learning models on the word-level language identification of the dataset is given in Table 2. Among traditional machine learning models, SVM performed the best with a macro-F1 score of 93.99%. However, this is lower than the performance of the BiLSTM-CRF and transformer models (by 2.01% and 1.57%, respectively).

Table 2. Performance of various models on the task of word-level language identification of Telugu-English code-mixed data

	Macro			Weighted			Accuracy
	Precision	Recall	F1score	Precision	Recall	F1score	
Traditional ML models							
Logistic Regression	93.63	78.69	85.51	92.40	92.16	92.28	97.17
SVM	93.85	94.14	93.99	97.15	97.14	97.14	97.14
Random Forest	93.66	79.25	85.85	92.61	92.41	92.51	92.41
Gradient Boosting	88.03	71.90	79.15	87.20	85.81	86.50	85.81
Deep learning models							
BiLSTM-CRF	96.80	95.25	96.00	97.99	98.01	97.99	98.01
Transformer	96.30	94.84	95.56	97.85	97.86	97.85	97.87

The macro-F1 score of the BiLSTM-CRF model is 96.00%, and the weighted-F1 score is 97.99%. The class-wise performance is provided in Table 3. The low performance on named entity and other tags (91.31% and 95.19% respectively) reduced the macro-F1 score. Identification of named entities is difficult in social media text because it is written informally with no adherence to capitalization rules and incorrect spellings. Combining a Named Entity Recognition (NER) module with the language identification system is likely to improve performance.

The transformer model achieved a macro-F1 of 95.56% and weighted-F1 of 97.85%. Since it is not pretrained on Telugu-English code-mixed text and the dataset is relatively small (25,006 sentences), its performance is likely to improve with more data. Both BiLSTM-CRF and transformer models outperformed traditional methods: the BiLSTM-CRF captures bidirectional context, while the transformer leverages subword tokenization to handle noisy or unseen words.

Table 3. Class-wise performance of various models on the task of word-level language identification of Telugu-English code-mixed data

	TE			EN			NER			OTH		
	P	R	F	P	R	F	P	R	F	P	R	F
Traditional ML models												
Logistic Regression	99.37	97.38	98.36	98.29	98.60	98.44	88.36	92.44	90.36	87.18	95.25	91.04
SVM	98.83	98.35	98.59	98.04	98.76	98.40	90.18	88.29	89.23	88.36	91.15	89.73
Random Forest	90.76	99.72	95.03	95.66	94.44	95.04	92.59	62.46	74.60	95.63	60.38	74.03
Gradient Boosting	84.38	99.93	91.50	93.17	71.49	80.91	75.14	82.67	78.73	99.41	33.48	50.10
Deep learning models												
BiLSTM-CRF	98.49	99.18	98.83	98.41	98.92	98.66	93.81	88.95	91.31	96.47	93.94	95.19
Transformer	98.47	99.23	98.85	98.27	97.43	97.85	92.62	89.37	90.96	95.86	93.34	94.58

*P-precision,R-recall,F-macroF1score

Our features are designed with linguistic and empirical motivations—including phonetic similarity for transliteration handling, suffix patterns for morphology, and dictionary-based flags for ambiguity resolution. To assess their utility, we performed leave-one-out feature experiments. The results of this experiment are provided in Table 4. It is observed that leaving suffixes, prefixes, or phonetic encoding as features resulted in the largest drop in performance (0.59% for suffixes, 0.37% for prefixes, 0.28% for phonetic encoding) compared to other features. Overall, the results emphasize the significance of morphological and phonetic features in effectively modeling language boundaries and handling transliteration phenomena in Telugu-English code-mixed text.

Table 4. Results of leave-one-out experiments for BiLSTM-CRF language identification model

Feature left out	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1 score	Drop in F1 score
all features used	98.01	96.80	95.25	96.00	-
suffixes	97.71	96.30	94.58	95.41	0.59
prefixes	97.81	96.48	94.82	95.63	0.37
phonetics	97.83	96.47	95.00	95.72	0.28
next word	98.00	96.62	95.05	95.81	0.19
single character	97.95	96.78	94.98	95.84	0.16
English dictionary	97.97	96.73	95.08	95.88	0.12
Telugu dictionary	97.96	96.70	95.16	95.90	0.10
special characters	97.98	96.83	95.08	95.92	0.08
unambiguous word	97.98	96.83	95.10	95.93	0.07
tf-idf	97.97	96.84	95.08	95.93	0.07
length	97.98	96.72	95.19	95.93	0.07
starts with capital	97.98	96.86	95.08	95.94	0.06
all caps	97.98	96.87	95.09	95.95	0.05
previous word	97.98	96.72	95.24	95.96	0.04
previous second word	98.00	96.61	95.36	95.97	0.03
numdigit	98.01	96.94	95.12	95.99	0.01
next second word	97.99	96.75	95.29	95.99	0.01

3.2. Error Analysis

The BiLSTM-CRF confusion matrix shown in Table 5 indicates minimal misclassification for language tags, with most errors involving named entities and other tags. Of 1,988 unique named entities in the test set, only 55.23% appear in training set, leading to lower accuracy (88.95%) for named entities compared to language tags (99.18% for Telugu tags and 98.92% for English tags). Adding a dedicated NER module is likely to improve performance.

Table 5. Confusion matrix for BiLSTM-CRF model (True label vs Predicted label). Figures in percentages.

True Label	Telugu	English	Named Entities	Others
Telugu	99.18	0.20	0.48	0.14
English	0.57	98.92	0.37	0.14
Named Entities	6.54	3.45	88.95	1.06
Others	3.74	1.14	1.19	93.94

Understanding the limitations of the proposed system for language identification of Telugu-English code-mixed text is critical for future improvements. The number of incorrectly predicted tags in the test data is 1,311. We analyze these errors and classify them into distinct patterns to better understand the causes. Table 6 summarizes the distribution of errors in various categories.

Table 6. Distribution of errors in BiLSTM-CRF language identification model across various categories

Error category	Count	Percentage
Actual named entity but predicted as some other tag	436	33.26%
Multi-word named entities	122	9.31%
Predicted as NE because of first letter is in capital case	91	6.94%
Predicted as NE because of all letters are in capital case	20	1.53%
Subtotal (errors involving named entities)	669	51.03%
Ambiguous words	204	15.56%
Spelling mistakes	116	8.85%
Fusion words	106	8.09%
Abbreviations	26	1.98%
Single letter	17	1.30%
Other cases where model made genuine error confusing between various tags	173	13.20%
Total	1311	100.00%

The largest category of errors (51.03%) involved named entities, which the model failed to identify. Of these, 33.26% are person, location, or organization names (e.g., “Steve,” “England,” “Infosys”), while 9.31% are multiword entities (e.g., “Supreme Court,” “Mission Impossible”) that are tagged word by word rather than as a whole. Reliance on capitalization caused 8.47% of errors: words with an initial capital (6.94%) or all capitals (1.53%) are sometimes wrongly classified as named entities. Other error sources included ambiguous words (15.56%) that could belong to either language (e.g., “me” in English is used by a speaker to refer to himself or herself, whereas “me” in Telugu is possessive used to refer to things that belong to the person that the speaker is addressing), spelling errors (8.85%) such as “indrasti” for “industry,” and fusion words (8.09%) combining English and Telugu (e.g., “avardulu” from “award” + “lu”). Abbreviations and short forms (1.98%) like “IT” or “vlge” also confused the model, as did single-letter words (1.30%) such as “e”. Genuine misclassifications accounted for 13.20%, such as the English word “dosage” mislabeled as Telugu or the Telugu word “rusi” probably mistaken for the named entity “Russia.”

Overall, NER remains the main challenge, especially for multiword and hybrid forms. Dependence on features like capitalization also leads to systematic errors. Addressing these issues will require expanding coverage of ambiguous and fusion words and leveraging external resources such as gazetteers to better recognize named entities and abbreviations.

3.3. Corpus building

The BiLSTM-CRF language identification model enables automatic construction of a large Telugu-English code-mixed corpus from social media comments. From 50.82 million raw YouTube comments obtained as discussed in Section 2.1, preprocessing removed non-ASCII text, duplicates, blank lines, and comments under five words. The filtered set is passed through the BiLSTM-CRF model, and only comments with at least two Telugu and two English words are retained; those containing Hindi are excluded. The resulting dataset contains 3.6 million Telugu-English code-mixed comments, and we refer to it as TEEN 3.6M BC (Telugu-English code-mixed – 3.6 million - Builtup Corpus). It has an average comment length of 11.74 words. In a random sample of 1,000 comments, 94.6% are code-mixed, yielding a 95% confidence interval of [0.9320, 0.9600]. The sample mean Code Mixing Index (CMI) [30] is 0.3293 with a standard deviation of 0.1267, giving a 95% confidence interval of [0.3214, 0.3371].

The Bi-LSTM-CRF-based language identification model has thus tremendously reduced the work involved in collecting Telugu-English code-mixed text. Although the comments are sourced from YouTube videos that post only Telugu content, only 3.63 million comments out of the 50.82 million raw comments are code-mixed in nature and written in Roman script; that is, 92.86% of the raw comments are not code-mixed in nature. Manually selecting code-mixed comments is a time-consuming and laborious process. The language identification model has enabled the automatic collection of Telugu-English code-mixed text on a large scale. This large corpus can facilitate research on downstream tasks such as POS tagging, dependency parsing, NER, sentiment analysis, and LLM pretraining. It also supports sociolinguistic research on mixing patterns and provides a benchmark resource for future shared tasks.

4. RESOURCES

The TEEN 3.6M BC dataset [31] contains 3,630,567 Telugu-English code-mixed comments. The dataset is released publicly on [Huggingface](#) repository and can serve as a rich resource for advancing research in multilingual and social media-based natural language processing. We also publicly release the manually annotated language-tagged dataset of 25,006 comments on [Github](#), labelled with four categories- Telugu, English, Named Entity, and Others. We refer to this dataset as TEEN 25K AD (Telugu-English code-mixed– 25,000 Annotated Dataset). This corpus provides a high quality benchmark for training and evaluating code-mixed models, thereby contributing to the development of more robust multilingual NLP systems for low-resource and code-mixed settings.

5. CONCLUSION

Code-mixed text is common in multilingual communities, especially Telugu-English on social media. Collecting such data is challenging as it also contains monolingual comments, making word-level language identification essential. In this paper, we propose a system that classifies tokens into Telugu, English, Named Entity, or Other. Among several approaches, a BiLSTM-CRF model performed best, achieving a macro-F1 of 96%. Using this model, we built a 3.6 million-comment Telugu-English corpus, the largest to date, alongside a 25,006-comment manually annotated dataset, both released publicly. Future work includes adding Named Entity Recognition, explicit tagging of fusion and abbreviations, normalization of Romanization, and integrating POS tags and subword embeddings. Expanding resources via synthetic data and speech-to-text corpora is another promising direction.

DATA AVAILABILITY

The supporting data of this study are openly available on Github at https://github.com/sandeep-maddu/teen_corpus and on Huggingface at <https://huggingface.co/sandeepmaddu/teen3.6M/tree/main>.

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